

The Role of Intellectual Property in the Development of Climate Solutions

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Abstract:

Climate change discourse seats pre-eminently above other widespread menaces like crimes, poverty and terrorism; all of which have become major problems for humanity. This pre-eminence rests less on the fact that climate change is partly responsible for the increase in these other social problems, than the existential nature of its effect when left unattended. However, addressing the menace of climate change was initially very slow because of the different arguments it generated. It started with the arguments on whether or not there were actual changes in the climatic conditions of the earth that was worth serious discussion. Subsequently, the arguments about the exact causes of climate change, and on whom and how to apportion blames began to emerge. In spite of the above, some points about climate change have become trite. It is now agreed that there is an urgent need to tackle the effects of climate change collectively. The Paris Agreement for instance insists on a global goal of limiting global warming. Also, there is the consensus that, innovative technology can play a very crucial role in the attainment of the set goals of reducing greenhouse gas emissions through innovations in green technology as climate solutions. This paper highlights the role of intellectual property rights as a major driver of technological innovations specifically designed to help in climate change mitigation, taking into cognizance the provisions of on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights Agreements and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) Green. The nature and forms these innovations take, from invention to innovation and diffusion of such technology were also highlighted in this paper. This paper also touched on the 'debate' mainly between the Developed countries like the United Kingdom and United States that see a strong protection of intellectual property rights regime as important incentives in propelling innovations in climate solutions, and the Developing countries like Ecuador, India, South Africa, etc., that see such as an obstacle in the fight against climate change.

Keywords: Climate Change, Climate change Technology, Climate Solutions, Intellectual Property, Patent, TRIPS.

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1. INTRODUCTION

It has never been a subject of contention that the emergence of modern government remains one of the most important astonishments of human development, especially with efforts of the State¹ to regulate the affairs of the citizens. Despite the debate about the governmental use of its powers vis-à-vis the ‘owners’ of the powers,² die-hard anarchist would appreciate the fact that, but for the State, human development would have been retarded or even gone into permanent occlusion. The State has remained steadfast in protecting the rights of the individual, and also his property rights. It was also quick to appreciate the intellectual contributions of the individuals by extending this protection to their non-physical properties. The totality of the protection of these intellectual based rights of individuals are now summed up under the label - Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs). As Granstrand summed it:

The use of property-like rights to induce innovations of various kinds is perhaps the oldest institutional arrangement that is particular to innovation as a social phenomenon. It is now customary to refer to these rights as intellectual property rights (IPRs), comprising old types of rights such as patents for inventions, trade secrets, copyrights, trademarks, and design rights, together with newer ones such as breeding rights and database rights. The various IPRs usually have long legal and economic histories, often with concomitant controversies.³

In the main, intellectual property refers to ‘a loose cluster of legal doctrines that regulate the uses of different sorts of ideas and insignia’.⁴ The term covers copyright, patents, trademarks and industrial designs.

¹ Not to be confused with municipal territories like the State of California or Delta State of Nigeria. Here, the State refers to a people permanently occupying a fixed territory, bound together by common law, habits and custom into a body polity, expressing through the medium of an organized government, independent sovereignty and control over all persons and things within its boundaries, capable of making war and peace and of entering into international relations with other communities of the globe. See, *United States v Kusche* DC, Cal 56 F Supp 202, 208. However, for more on the definition, and on the distinction between state, nation and nation-state, see EA Ifidon, ‘Introduction to International Studies and Diplomacy’, in, *Themes in International Studies and Diplomacy*, edited by FIA Omu and LE Otoide (Department of History and International Studies, University of Benin 2002).

² See generally, GH Sabine, *A History of Political Theory* (4th ed, Dryden Press 1973).

³ Ove Granstrand, ‘Innovation and Intellectual Property Rights Get access Arrow’, in Jan Fagerberg and David C. Mowery (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of Innovation* (Oxford Academic Books 2009). As we shall see in the course of this report, the controversies are little above academic exercises. This is particularly evident in the debate over the misconception that IPRs regimes serves to hinder the transfer of climate innovations to Developing countries.

⁴ William Fisher, ‘Theories of Intellectual Property’ <<https://cyber.harvard.edu/people/tfisher/iptheory.pdf>>

Intellectual property rights serve to protect the intellectual inputs that ultimately brought about the thing capable of being seen as a property. As has been noted, ‘the aim of every inventor, visionary or innovator is primarily to profit from the creation or works of his hands. Therefore, the presence of a framework to facilitate the protection of his creation – intellectual property – will only spur efficiency, productivity and more innovation’.⁵ Intellectual Property rights are not different from other physical property rights, which the state must protect as against invaders or trespassers. But unlike the physical rights to tangible property, the protection of the intellectual property rights of the inventor to reap from the fruit of his labour has to be moderated against the overall needs of the society to unrestricted quest for knowledge. However, attaining this position – to protect the intellectual input of the author on the one hand, and the needs of the knowledge quest of the society on the other hand – has proven to be a major task for those involved in this jurisprudential dilemma. As we shall see, this dilemma gets even more compounded with issues of patents dealing with climate technologies.

With few exceptions, it has become common knowledge that the climatic condition of the earth crust is increasingly becoming adverse as a result of human activities aimed at improving life on earth. While these activities are necessarily for human survival, there is the urgent need to halt, and where possible reverse the deleterious trends in the climatic condition of the earth now termed as Climate Change. Climate Change refers to a long-term shift in global or regional climate patterns. It refers to the ‘change in climate attributed directly or indirectly to human activity which, in addition to natural climate variability, is observed over comparable time periods’.⁶ Climate Change refers to a ‘change in the state of the climate that can be identified by changes in the mean and, or the variability of its properties and that persists for an extended period, typically decades or longer.

Climate change may be due to natural internal processes or external forces or to persistent anthropogenic changes in the composition of the atmosphere or in land use’.⁷ The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) defined it as, ‘a change of climate which is attributable directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over a comparable time periods’.⁸ These changes occasioned by the alterations of the composition of the global atmosphere come with major disturbing effects of on the living condition of the earth crust. From heat waves, to

⁵ Duale Ovia and Alex-Adedipe, ‘Patent as a tool to drive innovation’, *Businessday*, April 27, 2017 <<https://businessday.ng/news/legal-business/article/patent-tool-drive-innovation>> accessed 14 August 2023

⁶ David D Houghton, ‘Introduction to Climate Change: Lecture Notes for Meteorologists’ WMO-No 926, *World Meteorological Organization*, Geneva – Switzerland <https://library.wmo.int/doc_num.php?explnum_id=8968>

⁷ IPCC.

⁸ United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change 1992.

deforestation and desertification, from drought to major wildfires, the negative effects of climate change are legion, and detrimental to human existence.

However, increased focus on the effect of climate change has ceased to be the preoccupation of most scientist and policy-makers. The effect has become too evident to deny. Rather, efforts in the past few decades have focussed on how best to redress the effect of climate change. Here, two major policy responses have been suggested and accepted. These are the 'Mitigation' and the 'Adaptation' strategies.⁹ Both of these strategies rely on deliberate actions of individuals and governments, whether through re-orientation or the development of technologies to assist in combatting the negative impacts of climate change. In all, climate solutions have been accepted as a way forward in the fight to rescue the globe from the realities of adverse climate conditions.

Climatic Solutions,¹⁰ especially efforts at reducing our reliance on fossil fuels have been identified as a major tool for redressing the effects of Climate Change. These solutions, in the diverse forms are based on very costly Research and Development (R&D) carried out by individuals, groups, institutions, organisations and governments. The cost of researches and development in making available climate solutions are expected to be recouped by the originators of the solutions through patents that help to secure their intellectual property rights in these products and ideas. In fact, beyond most other forms of patents,¹¹ patents involving climate solutions are seen as more important because of the very nature of the activities involved implicated in producing them. Aside the cost and time involved in the processes leading to creation of these solutions, there is the fact that some of these solutions cannot be adapted for use in some other venture besides climate solutions. This is because some climate solutions are specifically articulated to tackle the effects of climate change, alone. They cannot be converted for use in other areas.

Despite the above seemingly shortcomings on research and development on climate solutions, more and more individuals and groups are still involved in these activities that are geared towards addressing the effects of climate change, by working round the clock to provide climate change solutions. The different patent arrangements provided and recognised around the world have been the main incentives for the continue push for climate change solutions.

We see therefore that, despite the arguments that we shall highlight in the course of this report, innovation is a veritable way to tackle climate change. And an adequate patent regime is a crucial incentive that drives the required R&D that drives these innovations relating to climate solutions.

⁹ See, Gianmarco Petroni, 'IPRs and Climate Change: the issue of the Technology Transfer', *LUISS* 2019.

¹⁰ Also refers to as 'environmentally sensitive technologies', 'environmentally friendly technologies', green technologies', etc. As we shall see shortly, these include, reducing the reliance on fossil fuel, greater energy efficiency, renewable energy, etc.

¹¹ In spheres such as software, technology hardware, biopharmaceuticals, and in automotive sector.

2. MEANING AND FORMS OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS (IPRS)

Intellectual property is a form of knowledge which societies have decided can be assigned specific property rights. To Posner and Landes:

... ideas, inventions, discoveries, symbols, images, expressive works (verbal, visual, musical, theatrical), or in short, any potentially valuable human product (broadly, 'information') that has an existence separable from a unique physical embodiment, whether or not the product has actually been 'propertized', that is, brought under a legal regime of property rights.¹²

Intellectual property signifies 'a loose cluster of legal doctrines that regulate the uses of different sorts of ideas and insignia'.¹³ It refers to the creations of the mind; these include inventions, literary and artistic works, and symbols, names, images, and designs used in commerce.¹⁴

IPRs have some resemblance to ownership rights over physical property like land, which is created and secured by law.¹⁵ In the words of Bentham:

Law does not say to man, labour, and I will reward you; but it says; Labour, and I will assure to you the enjoyment of the fruits of your labour—that natural and sufficient recompense which without me you cannot preserve; I will insure it by arresting the hand which may seek to ravish it from you. If industry creates, it is law which preserves; if at the first moment we owe all to labour, at the second moment, and at every other, we are indebted for everything to law.¹⁶

The idea of property and proprietary right first applied solely to tangible property and as such, when we speak of ownership of property, the first idea that comes to mind is things we can see, touch, or handle. Such items are cars, books, landed properties, and so on. Today, this has extended to reach intangible items such as shares, and even copyright,

¹² RA Posner and WM Landes, *The Economic Structure of Intellectual Property Law* (Belknap Press of Harvard University Press 2003), cited in David Weder, 'IP Rights and Their Effect on Innovation' <https://www.mckendree.edu/academics/scholars/issue6/weder.htm>

¹³ Fisher (n 4).

¹⁴ WIPO, IP Handbook.

¹⁵ For instance in Nigeria, irrespective of the traditional means by which a portion of land has been acquired, the Law is still required for the protection of the rights to use and own it. See, the Land Use Act 1978; *Ajiboye v Ishola* (2006) All FWLR 331, 1230. Cf: *Idundun v Okumagba* (1976) 9-10 SC.

¹⁶ Jeremy Bentham, *THE THEORY OF LEGISLATION III*; cited Weder (n 12)

hence we speak of *choses* in action.¹⁷ By reason of this shift in things that can be owned, creative ideas may now be validly owned if such ideas are reduced into an expressed form and they meet other relevant criteria. This is manifested in the concept of intellectual property.

Rights under intellectual property are divided into two broad categories - industrial property and copyright. Industrial property includes the following: inventions (patents), trademarks, industrial designs, and geographical indications of source. Copyright includes the following: literary and artistic works such as novels, poems and plays, films, musical works, artistic works such as drawings, paintings, photographs and sculptures, and architectural designs. Furthermore, the following rights are protected by copyright performing artists in their performances, producers of phonograms in their recordings, and those of broadcasters in their radio and television programs.¹⁸

Patent law protects inventions that demonstrate technological progress. Copyright law protects a variety of literary and artistic works, including paintings, sculpture, prose, poetry, plays, musical compositions, dances, photographs, motion pictures, radio and television programs, sound recordings, and computer software programs. Trademark law protects words, slogans, and symbols that serve to identify different brands of goods and services in the marketplace.¹⁹ IPRs can be seen principally as economic or commercial rights. They can also be compared to political or human rights. The TRIPS agreement treats them in the former sense, while recognizing the need to strike a balance between the rights of inventors and creators to protection, and the rights of users of technology.²⁰ Intellectual property has increasingly assumed a vital role with the rapid pace of technological, scientific and medical innovation that we are witnessing today. Moreover, changes in the global economic environment have influenced the development of business models where intellectual property is a central element establishing value and potential growth.

According to Landes and Posner, ‘the distinctive characteristics of most intellectual products, are that they are easily replicated and that enjoyment of them by one person does not prevent enjoyment of them by other persons’.²¹ Those characteristics in combination create a danger that the creators of such products will be unable to recoup their ‘costs of expression’ (the time and effort devoted to writing or composing and the costs of negotiating with publishers or record companies), because they will be undercut by copyists who bear only the low ‘costs of production’ and thus can offer

¹⁷ A third category of rights other than the above has come up owing to the emergence of Cryptoassets.

¹⁸ Ibid.

¹⁹ Adekola Tolulope Anthony and Eze Sunday Chinedu, ‘Intellectual Property Rights in Nigeria: A Critical Examination of the Activities of the Nigerian Copyright Commission’ <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/281745384_Intellectual_Property_Rights_in_NigeriaA_Critical_Examination_of_the_Activities_of_the_Nigerian_Copyright_Commission> accessed 5 July 2023

²⁰ Article 7 of TRIPS.

²¹ WM Landes and RA Posner, ‘An Economic Analysis of Copyright Law’ (1989) 18 *Journal of Legal Studies* 325.

consumers identical products at very low prices.²² Accordingly, ‘the government is continuously involved in the creation of intellectual property rights through the issuance of patents, copyrights and trademarks’.²³ These are highlighted below.

I. Patent

According to WIPO, ‘A patent is a legally binding monopoly granted by government to inventors to exclude others from manufacturing, selling or using the patented invention, without the patentee’s consent for a defined period usually 20 years’.²⁴ The grant of monopoly allows the patent owner or its assignees the exclusive right to exploit the patented invention as trade-off between him (the patentee) and the government for the disclosure of the invention.²⁵ The fundamental role of the patent system from an economist’s perspective is to address market failure and restore the incentives to invest in production of knowledge.

The patent system is intended to correct market failure and under-provision of innovative activities by providing innovators with exclusive rights to prevent others from exploiting their inventions without the patentee’s consent. To correct the potential inefficiencies of the market power which may be created through exclusive rights, the patent system provides for, among other mechanisms embedded in the system, public disclosure of the patented matter. The disclosure of the technical details of the invention through the patent system expands the public stocks of technical knowledge and creates competition among innovators. A third function of the patent system is to encourage technology transfer by creating tradable property rights to improve the efficiency of knowledge flows.²⁶

Unlike copyright, a patentee does not enjoy statutory rights automatically, unless he files an application for it to be registered. For instance, the law will readily grant the application of patent in respect of a drug manufactured by a similar process of existing patent drug that has a soporific effect if that new drug does not have this effect and still performs effectively the same function.²⁷ An applicant for a patent, upon the grant of his application becomes a patentee and enjoys the following rights: to preclude others from making, importing, selling or using the product on stocking it for the purpose of sale or use.²⁸

²² Ibid.

²³ Landes and Posner, cited Weder (n 12)

²⁴ WIPO Background Reading Material 1997

²⁵ Adebambo Adewopo, ‘Public Health, Access to Medicines and the Role of Patents System in Nigeria’, A keynote paper presented at the Roundtable of the Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies on the theme ‘Health Law and Policy’, at the Ayo Ajomo Auditorium, NIALS, Lagos on 19th May 2011

²⁶ WIPO, ‘Report on the International Patent System’, *Standing Committee On the Law of Patents*, Twelfth Session, World Intellectual Property Organization, Geneva, 3 February 2009

²⁷ See, *Ducros SA v Silas Industries and Trading Company Ltd* FHC/L/CS/1057/2003

²⁸ Foluke Dada, ‘Legal Effects of the Nigerian Patent Law on Sale of Drugs and Consumer Protection in Nigeria’ (2014) 14 *Global Journal of Human-Social Science: E Economics*, 6.1, 1

ii. Trade Marks

The term trademark refers to any word, phrase, symbol or design, or any combination of words, phrases, symbols or designs that identifies and distinguishes the source of the goods of one party from those of other parties. Similarly, service mark (which in some jurisdictions is also referred to as trademark) refers to any word, phrase, symbol or design, or any combination of words, phrases, symbols or designs, that identifies and distinguishes the services of one party from those of other parties.²⁹ So basically a trademark gives the owner of the mark the exclusive right to use the mark to identify goods or services and the owner in return for payment can give his mark to a third party. The duration of a trademark right varies but it can be renewed indefinitely beyond the initial period on payment of additional fees.³⁰ Trademark can be registered in a single country as most countries in the world today register and protect trademarks. However, trademarks can also be registered internationally such that the registration applies to other countries thereby avoiding registering separately in each country. WIPO administers an international system of trademark registration. This system of international registration is possible due to two major treaties, the Madrid Agreement Concerning the International Registration of Marks and the Madrid Protocol (WIPO).

iii. Industrial Designs

Industrial design plays an important role in the trading of consumer goods or products. Industrial designs on its part are what makes a product attractive and appealing; hence, they add to the commercial value of a product and increase its marketability. Today, industrial design has become an integral part of consumer culture where rival articles compete for consumer's attention. It has become important therefore, to grant to an original industrial design adequate protection.³¹ When an industrial design is protected, this helps to ensure a fair return on investment. An effective system of protection also benefits consumers and the public at large, by promoting fair competition and honest trade practices.

That apart, protecting industrial designs helps economic development, by encouraging creativity in the industrial and manufacturing sectors and contributes to the expansion of commercial activities and the export of national products. In the words of Odion and Ogba, 'industrial designs are those elements incorporated into mass-produced items that tend to enhance their attractiveness by their appearance'.³²

Industrial designs belong to the aesthetic field, but are at the same time intended to serve as pattern for the manufacture of products of industry or handicraft. An industrial design is the ornamental or aesthetic aspect of a useful article, which must appeal to the

²⁹ USPTO, International Trademark Association 2012.

³⁰ GB Ramello, 'What's In A Sign? Trademark Law and Economic Theory', (2006) 20 *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 4, 565.

³¹ Study Material: Professional Programme Intellectual Property Rights-Law and Practice, Module 3, Elective Paper 9.4, The Institute of Company Secretaries of India, 2014.

³² JO Odion, and NEO Ogba, *Essays on Intellectual Property Law* (Ambik, 2010) 112.

sense of sight and may consist of the shape and, or pattern and, or colour of article. An industrial design to be protectable, must be new and original. Industrial designs are protected against unauthorised copying or imitation, for a period which usually lasts for five, ten or 15 years.³³

Textile designs were the first to receive legal protection. As early as in 1787, the first Act for design protection was enacted in Great Britain for the encouragement of the arts of design. It is significant to note that when the designs law was codified in 1842 and took its modern-day shape, copyright protection had not yet been extended to drawings, paintings and photographs. This came only twenty years later with the enactment of the Fine Arts Copyright Act, 1862. Codification of copyright law was nowhere in sight and came only seventy years later with the enactment of the Imperial Copyright Act, 1911.³⁴ Also, until 1883, the statutes relating to patents, designs and trademarks remained separate. They were combined in a single enactment by the Patents, Designs, and Trade Marks Act, 1883, which repealed all the then existing statutes in the three areas. Soon trademarks law parted company and was separately enacted as the Trade Marks Act, 1905, leaving patents and designs to remain together. The Patents and Designs Act, 1907 consolidated the enactments relating to patents and designs.³⁵

iv. Copyright

Copyright is only one of other forms of property right as it falls within the broad spectrum of Intellectual Property Law. It is that branch of law that gives protection to the finest manifestation of human achievement.³⁶ The law of copyright as an intellectual property contemplates the protection of the rights of authors in the areas of literary works, musical works, artistic works, cinematograph films, sound recordings as well as broadcasts.³⁷ These represent works that arise as a result of creative endeavour and the law protects such expressed creative ideas in other to prevent one who has not expended energy and time in the creation of a work from reaping benefits unduly from it.

Also inherent in the law of copyright is the ancillary right given to users of copyrighted works subject to certain provisions as may be determined by the copyright legislation applicable. Thus, before a protected work may be used, an intending user must fulfil certain requirements flowing from the protection given to the intellectual work by the copyright law.

The use of property-like rights to induce innovations of various kinds is perhaps the oldest institutional arrangement that is particular to innovation as a social phenomenon. It is now customary to refer to these rights as intellectual property rights (IPRs), comprising old types of rights such as patents for inventions, trade secrets,

³³ Study Material: Professional Programme Intellectual Property Rights.

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ Ibid.

³⁶ Odion, and Ogba, *Essays on Intellectual Property Law*, 1

³⁷ S. 1(1) of the Copyright Act, Cap C 28 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 (as amended).

copyrights, trademarks, and design rights, together with newer ones such as breeding rights and database rights. The various IPRs usually have long legal and economic histories, often with concomitant controversies.

3. CLIMATE SOLUTIONS

That human activities impact negatively on climate change is presently generally accepted.³⁸ Adverse changes in climatic conditions of portions of the earth crust in on the increase according to figures presented by experts. Frequent increases in desertification, deforestation, drought, heat waves and wildfire, severe storms and floods, and other shifting weather patterns are indices of extreme weather condition as a result of climate change.³⁹ The realization and concerns for climate change have led different developed countries to come up with theories and methods to try and combat the effects of climate change. In fact, as Dimowo⁴⁰ noted:

Climate change has come to occupy the attention of Governments, who may disagree as to their different contributions to the present climatic situation, or the best approach to curbing the effect of climate change, but are in unison that there is urgent need to tackle the causes of climate change. Studies have been carried out with different themes and proliferated aims, but all bothering on the disturbing issue of climate change, particularly of its impact on the environment.'

These studies have been complemented by the works of concerned organizations,⁴¹ which have also worked to see how best to redress the menace of climate change. From these collaborations came the strategies of Mitigation and Adaptation, being the agreed strategies of curbing climate change.

In the main, mitigation strategy refers to the reduction of the environmental impact of climate change. Mitigation involves:

... reducing the flow of greenhouse gases that imprison heat into the atmosphere. This can be achieved either by reducing the use of fossil fuels used for transport and for

³⁸ See, AJ Porter, et al, 'Organizing Authority in the Climate Change Debate: IPCC Debates and the Management of Dialectical Tensions', (2017) 39 *Journal of Organization Studies* (7) 873; 'Global Warming and Climate Change' <https://pubs.acs.org/cen/coverstory/87/8751_cover.html> accessed 1 July 2023; 'An Inconvenient Truth' <<https://www.imdb.com/title/tt0497116>> accessed 3 July 2023.

³⁹ US Department of Agriculture, 'Climate Solutions' <<https://www.usda.gov/climate-solutions>>

⁴⁰ Folarin Dimowo, 'Climate Change in Nigeria: Environmental Impact on the Niger Delta' (Thesis, University of Benin, Nigeria, 2019)

⁴¹ 'Assessing the International response to Climate Change', <www.garnautreview.org.au/pdf/garnaut_chapter8.pdf> accessed 5 July 2023.

the production of heat and electricity, or by strengthening the 'sinks' that absorb these gases (trees, oceans and land). The aim of mitigation is to prevent human beings from interfering with the climate system so as to 'stabilize greenhouse gas levels within a time sufficient to ecosystems to adapt naturally to climate change, to ensure that food production is not threatened and to allow economic development to proceed sustainably'.⁴²

Mitigation also slows down the pace and magnitude of the effects of climate change, say for example, making use of fossil fuels in a more efficient manner, while simultaneously expanding forest resources to sequester larger amounts of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere.⁴³ Despite the need to be optimistic of the ideas behind mitigation, as a strategy for curbing climate change, it is generally agreed that great harm has already been done to the atmosphere through greenhouse gas emissions. This leads to the imperatives of adaptation.

Adapting to climate change connotes the 'progressive adaptation to the present or expected future climate'. The aim of adaptation as a strategy is to:

... limit our sensitivity to the dangerous effects of climate change. This also requires exploiting any potential beneficial opportunities linked to climate change. This approach requires a more strategic analysis between different sectors and the government concerned, in order to properly address the consequences of impacts and to ensure that adaptation measures are time effective. An adaptation strategy implies each sector to identify which are the most important actions to address future climate change.⁴⁴

Climate solutions that are aimed at achieving the mitigation and adaptation strategy have been further divided into two: natural climate solutions and technological based solutions.⁴⁵

Natural climate solutions as the name goes, are solutions that are based on the activities of nature. These are natural actions geared towards the protection, management and the restoration of nature so as to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and also to sequester carbon in the atmosphere. It has been observed that, when 'combined with

⁴² Report on Climate Change Mitigation of the United Nations Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change 2014, 4.

⁴³ Dimowo (n 40)

⁴⁴ NASA, 'Responding to Climate Change'. Cited in Petroni (n 9) 22.

⁴⁵ This is the one that is of concern to this paper.

transition away from fossil fuels, natural climate solutions offer immediate and cost-effective ways to tackle the climate crisis, while also supporting healthy, thriving communities and ecosystems'.⁴⁶ Noting further that, 'globally, natural climate solutions could deliver more than a third of the emission reductions needed by 2030 to avoid the worst impacts of climate change'.⁴⁷

Nonetheless, natural climate solutions cannot do it all. The efforts of nature have to be complemented by man-made solutions if the struggle to put down adverse climate change is to be fruitful. This is not out of place to conceive. Nature has limited role to play in the depletion of the ozone layer. Human activities bear much burden on the Earth crust, especially with the production activities of the developed countries.⁴⁸ For instance, the *SCIENTIFIC AMERICAN* noted that cement production is a major source of greenhouse gas emission. The Magazine noted that:

The US alone contributed 50.7 million metric tons of carbon dioxide to the atmosphere in 2005 from cement production, which requires heating limestone and other ingredients to 1,450 degrees Celsius (2,642 degrees Fahrenheit).⁴⁹

Interestingly, cement production will continue to be on the increase. It is a major component of infrastructural upgrade, which is also needed to reduce greenhouse gas emission. The way out of this conflict – the need for cement and the environmental effect of its production – is to improve on the process of making cement by using alternative fuels to fire up the furnace. Providing alternatives or more energy efficiency relies on climate solution either mitigation technologies or adaptation technologies.

The need to deploy technological climate solutions becomes even more imperative if the ambitious 'Six-Sector Solution to the Climate Crisis' as stated by UNEP is anything to go by. The Report noted that, 'the world is warming faster than at any point in recorded history'.⁵⁰ Adding that, there is urgent need to 'limit the spike in temperature to an average of 1.5°C above pre-industrial level'.⁵¹ The Report noted, rather emphatically, that ensuring a safe future below the 1.5°C mark requires the world to cut 30 gigatonnes

⁴⁶ 'Natural Climate Solutions', *The Nature Conservancy* <<https://www.nature.org/en-us/what-we-do/our-insights/perspectives/natural-climate-solutions>>

⁴⁷ Ibid.

⁴⁸ While Developed countries have been the major culprits in the production of greenhouse gas, the developing countries have acted in recent times like they have catching up to do. It has been noted that, 'since the 1990s, developing countries have seen a huge increase in their greenhouse gas emissions. To give an idea, only China has almost quadrupled its CO₂ emissions (364 percent), while India (278 percent), Indonesia (215 percent) and Saudi Arabia (202 percent) have increased dramatically their emissions'. Petroni (n 9) 18.

⁴⁹ David Biello, '10 Solutions for Climate Change', *SCIENTIFIC AMERICAN* <<https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/10-solutions-for-climate-change>>

⁵⁰ The United Nations Environment Programme UNEP.

⁵¹ Ibid.

greenhouse gas emissions annually by 2030. Transport and industry are not enough. We need to cut carbon emissions by managing our land and resources more efficiently, including building smart cities and curbing deforestation and food waste.⁵²

Fig. 1: Pie Chart showing the Six-Sector Solution to the Climate Crisis.⁵³

Climate solutions will remain a veritable tool in the fight against climate change. Natural climate solutions cannot cater for these exigencies. Technologically driven climate solutions will increasingly be relied upon for results in the fight to reduce climate change. Climate solutions come in different forms. Some of these are presented below:

‘Biomass: Solid fuels based on materials of non-mineral origin (animal or plant); engines operating on such fuels (e.g., wood).

Insulation: Elements or materials used for heat insulation; double-glazed windows.

⁵² Ibid.

⁵³ Extrapolated from UNEP's 2020 edition of the Emissions Gap Report

Heating: Heat pumps, central heating systems using heat pumps; energy recovery systems in air conditioning.

CCS: Extraction, transportation, storage, and sequestration of CO₂.

Cement: Natural pozzuolana cements; cements containing slag; iron ore cements; cements from oil shales, residues, or waste; calcium sulphate cements.

Electric vehicles: Electric propulsion of vehicles; regenerative braking; batteries; control systems specially adapted for hybrid vehicles.

Geothermal: Use of geothermal heat; devices for producing mechanical power from geothermal energy.

Hydro: Hydropower stations; hydraulic turbines; submerged units incorporating electric generators; devices for controlling hydraulic turbines.

Lighting: Compact fluorescent lamps; electroluminescent light sources.

Methane: Equipment for anaerobic treatment of sludge; biological treatment of wastewater or sewage; anaerobic digestion processes; apparatus aiming at collecting fermentation gases.

Marine: Tide or wave power plants; mechanisms using ocean thermal energy conversion; water wheels.

Solar: Solar photovoltaic (conversion of light radiation into electrical energy), including solar panels; concentrating solar power (solar heat collectors having lenses or reflectors as concentrating elements); solar heat (use of solar heat for heating and cooling).

Waste: Solid fuels based on industrial residues or waste materials; recovery of heat from waste incineration; production of energy from waste or waste gases; recovery of waste heat from exhaust gases.

Wind: Wind motors; devices aimed at controlling such motors'.⁵⁴

Added to the above forms of climate technologies is the idea of geoengineering. This involves capturing carbon dioxide before it is released and storing it in some fashion, either deep beneath the earth, at the bottom of the ocean or in carbonate minerals. Such carbon capture and storage are critical to any serious effort to combat climate change'.⁵⁵

⁵⁴ Petroni, (n 9) 19-21

⁵⁵ Biello, '10 Solutions for Climate Change'.

This is a capital-intensive approach to climate change, but it is considered as among the drastic means for mitigating the effect of climate change.

4. THE LITERATURE ON IPRS AND CLIMATE CHANGE TECHNOLOGIES

The correlation between the very pressing need to address negative changes in the climatic conditions of the earth crust through climate technologies/solutions on the one hand, and the encouragement and protection of such innovations through intellectual property rights on the other hand has remained controversial. While most of the policy makers, commentators and academicians on this subject agree that intellectual property rights indeed stimulate innovations that could be germane to fighting climate change by protecting the proprietary interests of owners of these climate technologies, some others see IPRs as capable of creating an unwanted bottleneck in the flow of technologies that are expected to aid in the fight against climate change.

Kujo⁵⁶ examines the complex relationship that exist between IPRs and climate change, especially the relevant legal issues and presenting legal answers through the prisms of important discussions on related disciplines. It basically focuses on the relationship between IPRs and how they interface with issues of climate change. The author agrees that, 'mechanisms for protecting intellectual property rights can be crucial in the ongoing efforts to deal with and mitigate climate change on a national and international level',⁵⁷ and that, such 'would be accomplished by granting intellectual property rights a technology-based reductions in emissions and with reference to sustainable development laws',⁵⁸

Like most authors, Kujo also believes that:

... mechanisms for protecting intellectual property rights can be crucial in the ongoing efforts to deal with and mitigate climate change on a national and international level. This would be accomplished by granting intellectual property rights a technology-based reductions in emissions and with reference to sustainable development laws'.⁵⁹

However, the imperatives of combatting climate change seem to supersede considerations of right protection under IPRs. Therefore, the fundamental justification for IPR system

⁵⁶ EM Kujo, 'Intellectual Property Rights as a Key Driver in Climate Change Mitigation', (2022) 13 Nnamdi Azikiwe University Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence, No. 2 <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/naujilj/article/view/233140/220223>

⁵⁷ Ibid.

⁵⁸ Ibid.

⁵⁹ EM Kujo, 'Intellectual Property Rights as a Key Driver in Climate Change Mitigation' (2022) 13 *NAUJILJ* 2, 87

that is wealth based has to be moderated because of the existential challenge of climate change.

The thesis by Petroni⁶⁰ set out to analyse the most critical on issues involving the transfer of green technologies. The author also sought to understand if IPRs is an obstacle to the transfer of new technologies. The central argument on the role of IPRs and climate solutions were articulated by the author, thus: ‘while developed countries see them as a strong mechanism that incentivizes innovation through the provision of exclusive rights, developing countries, not having the resources to invest in R&D or to pay licenses, consider IP as a formidable obstacle to the transfer of green technologies’.⁶¹

Addressing this impasse requires serious policy orientation. According to Petroni, three factors have to be taken into consideration on issues of policies for climate change, which is expected to improve of sustainable development in developing countries. These include the social impact of those choices; the economic point of view and the formalization of policies itself.⁶² In this sense, policymakers need to be more result-oriented; by tilting more on the side of considerations about climate change by allowing freer transfer of climate technologies to developing countries.

Maruf Sanni⁶³ et al, surprisingly come with a minority opinion. They stated that the existing IPRs do not stop African countries from developing climate technologies as obtainable in the developed countries. The authors noted that, ‘African countries lack capacities to adapt, develop, deploy and operate high low-carbon technologies which can give them competitive advantage in the global market’. The authors suggested that, African states need to create an institutional set-up to disseminate innovative strategies to accelerate and facilitate the development and diffusion of climate technologies.

K. Raiser⁶⁴ et al., also noted the problem of patent vis-à-vis the development and dissemination of climate technologies globally. Their article recognised the place of patent as an important economic incentive in the development of technologies; they however insist that there is the need for access to climate technologies all over the world. The authors argue that technologies of climate change involve predominantly an improvement on existing technology, and so patent may end up restricting these developments because of lack of access to these technologies in the first place. They noted that,

...although patents provide a strong economic incentive for innovation, they limit the further commercialization of

⁶⁰ Petroni (n 9).

⁶¹ Ibid.

⁶² Ibid.

⁶³ Maruf Sanni, Caleb M. Adelowo, David A. Ogunkanbi, Adesina A. Oyewale, Abolaji D. Dada, & Bamidele R. Muritala, ‘Climate Change and Intellectual Property Rights in Africa: Environmental necessity-economic opportunity’, (2016) 8 *African Journal of Science, Technology, Innovation and Development*, Issue 5-6.

⁶⁴ K Raiser, H Naims, T Bruhn, ‘Corporatization of the climate? Innovation, intellectual property rights, and patents for climate change mitigation’, (May 2017) 27 *Elsevier Energy Research & Social Science*, 1-8

mitigation technologies based on previously patented materials and thus hinder global access to mitigation solutions. Development of mitigation technologies, specifically of renewable energies and carbon capture storage, requires predominantly an improvement of existing technologies. Therefore, patents are seen to restrict development and are perceived as an obstacle to climate change mitigation.

K. Raiser, et al concluded and agreed that climate change has potentially catastrophic consequences on mankind; however, the different patent regimes have to be improved upon to allow access to the development and implementation of climate technologies.

The Report by Robert Burrell, et al.,⁶⁵ deviated from the regular arguments seen above. Their work sought to understand whether the current IPRs system curtail or promote transfer and innovation of climate technologies in developing countries. The work attempted to answer this question through the systematic review theoretical and empirical literature as well as interviews with innovation experts in developing countries. The summary of the findings of Robert Burrell, et al. is instructive. According to them:

... the heated debate on IPRs and climate technology overstates the relevance of IP law as a barrier to the diffusion of climate technology in developing countries. Greater awareness about the instruments that prioritise climate technology diffusion (rather than invention) may be a more impactful approach. This includes strengthening the incentives to create reliable, strong domestic demand in developing nations, which includes the creation of more stringent climate policy.⁶⁶

Flowing from the above, the authors noted that:

... achieved by adopting instruments that reduce local deployment costs, provide targeted financial and technological support, and help in creating domestic climate-related technological and economic absorptive capacities that enable developing countries to produce and maintain climate technologies themselves. A global policy framework for climate technology diffusion needs to be inclusive, ensuring a fair distribution of economic

⁶⁵ Robert Burrell, et al., 'Intellectual Property Rights, Climate Technology Transfer and Innovation in Developing Countries' *New Economic Thinking*, August 2023, <https://www.inet.ox.ac.uk/files/intellectual-property-rights-2023-14.pdf>

⁶⁶ Ibid.

opportunities in a climate-sound economy, whilst considering the future direction of improvements to existing measures that could exclude developing countries from participation (e.g. Border Carbon Adjustments).⁶⁷

The authors concluded that, IPRs do not have much relevance in terms of diffusion of most climate solutions in developing countries. Adding that, ‘there is no clear rationale in favour of, nor against, weakening IP protection under the TRIPS Agreement⁶⁸ such as an IP waiver over climate technologies’.⁶⁹

5. IPRS AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF CLIMATE SOLUTIONS

The arguments will continue into the foreseeable future about the role of IPRs in the development of technology, especially as in this case, climate solutions. Even the debate over reality climate change in general is still raging despite abundance of evidence indicating the deleterious effect of negative changes in climatic condition of the earth crust. For one reason or the other, there is bound to be a contrary or antagonistic view to any development.

Therefore, with time, the stringent positions of the protagonists will need to be moderated. This is expected in the debate over the role of IPRs and the transfer of climate solutions under the current patent regimes. The need for stronger protective IPRs to promote innovations, a position of the United States and its developed partners on the one hand,⁷⁰ may need to yield in favour of the position of states like Ecuador, South Africa and other Developing countries who insist that these technologies be more accessible since the fight in a global cause.⁷¹

For those that have come to agree to the existence of climate change, with its attendant consequence on mankind, and that technology is an important tool for controlling or redressing the negative effects of climate change, there also exist the consensus that IPRs and climate technologies are inseparable. That is, there is a general agreement that IPRs is the bedrock for the development of technology, including climate solutions. As a genre of property rights, IPRs serves basically for the protection of the proprietary interest of the right holder. Especially of Patents, it allows the patent owner the monopoly of enjoyment of rights accruing as a result of his labour and finances that

⁶⁷ Ibid.

⁶⁸ The WTO Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) was passed in 1994 at the conclusion of the Uruguay Round. It is currently the primary global IPR treaty.

⁶⁹ Ibid.

⁷⁰ It is reported that six industrialised countries of Japan, the United States, Germany, the Republic of Korea, the United Kingdom, and France accounted for almost 80% of patent filings in clean energy generation technologies.

⁷¹ See, ‘Item 11 Contribution of Intellectual Property to Facilitate the Transfer of Environmentally Rational Technology’, Extracted from Document IP/C/M/76/Add.1, being an Extract from Minutes of Meeting of the Council for Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights, Held In The Centre William Rappard on 11 JUNE 2014.

were expended in developing the product. This is also known as ‘labour theory of value’, which is the same theory of physical property. Here the labour which the individual has put in to realise the property automatically justifies his ownership of same. Giovanetti noted:

... because of the property-rights model of innovation, where those who invest their time, money creativity and effort in developing new products and services get to direct their own efforts, own the results and profit from their inventions.⁷²

This idea of proprietary rights of ownership aligns with the innate characteristics of man as basically materialistic. This was captured by the statement of Niccolo Machiavelli, that, ‘men weep more over the loss of their property than of their fathers’!⁷³ Thomas Hobbes was even more explicit when he explained the emergence of the Commonwealth as a result of man’s need to reap from the fruits of his labour and that his descendant should enjoy same. To him:

The Passions that encline men to Peace, are Feare of Death; Desire of such things as are necessary to commodious living; and a Hope by their Industry to obtain them. And Reason suggesteth convenient Articles of Peace, upon which men may be drawn to agreement.⁷⁴

From the above therefore, Abraham Lincoln was right when he stated that, ‘the Patent System added the fuel of interest to the fire of genius.’⁷⁵ David Weder expanded this by stating that:

Intellectual property laws encourage innovation by allowing individuals and firms to stake out IP rights thereby protecting their investments in research and development.... Absent patent protection, there would be nothing to prevent a competitor from reverse engineering ... in order to produce a generic version.... Innovation would thus be discouraged and, as a direct consequence, economic growth would be restricted.⁷⁶

⁷² Tom Giovanetti, ‘Intellectual Property and Its Discontents’, *The Washington Post*, October 14, 2004. [Emphasis mine]

⁷³ Niccolo Machiavelli, *The Prince* (Penguin, 1975), intro.

⁷⁴ Thomas Hobbes, *Leviathan* (Touchstone, 1997), 208.

⁷⁵ Quoted in Weder (n 12).

⁷⁶ Ibid.

The research and development of a product or technology involves the gamut of activities, including intellectual and physical that are necessary for transforming an idea into a valuable product. This process starts immediately the development a prototype through to the period where the product owner *may* get a financial for the harnessing of the product; a phase that industrial experts describe as ‘the valley of death’.⁷⁷ Patentability of the technology only becomes feasible upon survival of this phase where it may come under the ambit of Article 27(1) of the TRIPS.⁷⁸ Article 27 (1) reads thus:

1. Subject to the provisions of paragraphs 2 and 3, patents shall be available for any inventions, whether products or processes, in all fields of technology, provided that they are new, involve an inventive step and are capable of industrial application. Subject to paragraph 4 of Article 65, paragraph 8 of Article 70 and paragraph 3 of this Article, patents shall be available and patent rights enjoyable without discrimination as to the place of invention, the field of technology and whether products are imported or locally produced.

With this act, the patent owner secures the right to enjoy the use of the product exclusively for the period of 20 years, subject to some of the provisions of TRIPS. Similarly, patent serves as a source of information to the interested members of the public. Since it is likened to a contract between the inventor and the Government, by which ‘the inventor gives a public disclosure in return for a limited monopoly for a certain period of time, after which the public is free to use the invention. After a patent expires, it cannot be renewed; anyone may then use the patented invention without the inventor’s permission.’⁷⁹

This public disclosure or the need for knowledge of the workings of such technology is very key crucial to the current regime of IPRs. Article 7 of the World Trade Organisation (WTO) Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) provides thus:

The protection and enforcement of intellectual property rights should contribute to the promotion of technological innovation and to the transfer and dissemination of technology, to the mutual advantage of producers and users of technological knowledge and in a manner conducive to

⁷⁷ U. S. Department of Energy, ‘From Invention to Innovation: Commercialization of new technology by independent and small business investors’, 1991.

⁷⁸ The WTO Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights.

⁷⁹ ‘Frequently asked questions: Patent’ https://ipindia.gov.in/writereaddata/Portal/Images/pdf/Final_FREQUENTLY_ASKED_QUESTIONS_-PATENT.pdf

social and economic welfare, and to a balance of rights and obligations.⁸⁰

The implication of the above is that with patent, the interested public can have access to the technology. This has been noted to be a major boost for further innovations and inventions. As noted by Savale and Savale:

Once a patent expires, the protection ends, and an invention enters the public domain, that is the owner no longer holds exclusive rights to the invention, which becomes available to commercial exploitation by others. All patent owners are obliged, in return for patent protection, to publicly disclose information on their invention in order to enrich the total body of technical knowledge in the world. Such an ever-increasing body of public knowledge promotes further creativity and innovation in others. In this way, patents provide not only protection for the owner but valuable information and inspiration for future generations of researchers and inventors.⁸¹

It is in recognition of the above that the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) came up with the WIPO GREEN in 2013. The WIPO Green is an 'an online platform for technology exchange that will contribute to the accelerated adaptation, adoption and deployment of green technology solutions by connecting technology providers with technology seekers. As a tech-matching platform, WIPO Green was created to connect potential technology users and technology providers, and to favour the exchange of green technologies.⁸²

The Green Technology Book 2022: Solutions for climate change adaptation was undertaken by WIPO to complement the works of the WIPO Green, and also to canvass for Adaptation solutions specifically. This is because, adaptation technologies are not being freely transferred by the Developed countries the way mitigation technologies are being transferred.⁸³

The WIPO Green Technology Book groups climate technologies into three:

- 9 Proven technologies which have been around for some time and are well tested;
- 10 Frontier technologies which are new, less well-tested but available; and

⁸⁰ Emphasis mine.

⁸¹ Sagar Kishor Savale and Varsha Kishor Savale, 'Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)', (2016) 5 *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 6, 2529-2559, 2531.

⁸² To its credit, the WIPO Green currently has nearly 130,000 entries from around the globe that connects parties together.

⁸³ WIPO Green Technology Book 2022, 12

- 11 Horizon technologies which are near-future solutions expected on the market within the foreseeable future.⁸⁴

The concepts of innovation, solutions and technology often used interchangeably as in the case in this report were clearly distinguished. According to the Green Technology Book:

... the term innovation to cover all intellectual creativity that can result in a solution. Solution broadly means to deploy the output of this innovation to solve a specific challenge. Technology is a broad term, but we apply it more narrowly to any physical entity or technique, with or without additional equipment, that is deployed to resolve a specific challenge.⁸⁵

Of utmost relevance to the point of discussion in this report is the connection of technological knowledge in the international patent system. Green Technology Book noted that an inventor of a new solution is more secured under the IPR on the invention. The Book added that:

The legal protection conferred by an IPR is an important measure against unauthorized use of an invention. It is also in effect a market tool that allows an inventor to recoup investment in R&D through a government-sanctioned competitive advantage for a fixed period of time. Although usually commercially oriented, an IPR may also be relevant for any inventor who wishes to control their invention's release into the public domain but without benefitting commercially.

In essence, the Green Technology Book makes bare the correlation between IPRs and the development of climate solutions, since the former helps clarify ownership, strengthens the bargaining power of the patent holder, helps attract potential partners and funding, all of which aid technological transfer.

6. CONCLUSION

The effects of climate change are increasingly evident needing contrary arguments. The focus has now assumed seeking the most viable means of contending with the excruciating effects of climate change. Two approaches have been identified as pathways through which this could be achieved. These are through mitigation and adaptation strategies. Technological innovations have also been recognized capable of providing the solutions to the fight against climate change.

The importance of intellectual property rights at the international level has been penned as intricately linked to successful development of climate solutions. The role of

⁸⁴ Ibid.

⁸⁵ Ibid., 15

IPRs is vital. As we have seen, climate solutions are capital intensive projects. They are usually produced after serious efforts in Research and Development. Research and Development are capital intensive. Therefore, even though the existential nature of climate change requires an altruistic approach, investors in the production of climate solutions are expected to recoup the cost they have put in to make their contribution possible. No other property rights regime has the ability to help inventors reap adequately from their investments than IPRs.

We should jettison the arguments put forward by developing countries that IPRs hinders the transfer of climate change technology. This hindrance is more apparent than real. The developed countries bear the bulk of the responsibility for climate change as a result of their diverse and massive production industries debuted since the Industrial Revolution in Europe in 1840s. Accordingly, while the developed countries have hoarded Patents over technological innovations in the past, the imperatives of a concerted effort over climate change have imposed on them the responsibility to share climate solutions with developing countries. Rather than to put it to the developed countries that they have refused to allow for the diffusion of climate technologies, developing countries should look inwards and ask the pertinent question: are they really ready to support the fight to curb climate change?

The question is important. As we have it, most of these countries are still contending with issues such as irrigation, storage of excess produces and even transition from one legitimate government to another. These impediments are very rudimentary compared with ambitious programmes of climate change solutions. The insight from the WIPO Green Technology Book is apostate to and revealing of these points. According to it,

Often, a new technology will need adapting to local conditions and complex systems may have to be in place for a solution to work properly. This requires the receiving country or region to be capable of creating the right conditions for a solution to work. This can entail having adequate education or training, a stable electricity supply, a communication and internet connection, reliable transport and delivery systems, a functioning legal system, efficient financial services, an openness to trade, a well-functioning and sizeable market, and peace and stability.⁸⁶

From the foregoing, we see that the developing countries have more work to do internally to make them amenable to climate change technologies, rather than blaming the developed countries almost unnecessarily. This being said, IPRs is expected to continue to create the confidence needed by investors embarking of the development of climate

⁸⁶ WIPO (n 83), 28.

solutions in the coming period. While further moderations are expected from International IPRs regimes such as WIPO and WTO-TRIPS, patent protection will remain the main vehicle for providing incentives to investors.